

Organisational Commitment and Organisational Culture to Enhancing of Job Performance

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Article Info	Abstract
<p><i>Article History</i></p> <p>Received: August 14, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 15, 2022</p>	<p><i>Job performance is a measure to determine individual performance in contributing to a job. It often occurs in employees who have high knowledge and skills, but have low job performance. Some of the factors affecting work performance are Organisational Commitment and Organisational Culture. Organisational commitment is the level where employees identify organisational goals and hope to maintaining their member in the organisation. Meanwhile, organisational culture are values and norms the directly influence on behavior of members in organisation. This aims was toknew to effect the Organisational Commitment and Organisational Culture toward Job Performance. The research will be conducted at Bank X, one of the commercial banks at the city of Bandung in Indonesia, involving 80 employees. The sampling technique was carried out by a simple random method. The technique of data analysis is uses the path analysis. The research results shows that there waseffect of Organisational Commitment and Organisational Culture on Job Performance was both partially and simultaneously significant. High employee commitment in the organisation leads to high job performance. Likewise, a strong Organisational Culture within the Bank leads to high Job Performance.</i></p>
<p>Keywords : Organisational Commitment,Organisational Culture,Job Performance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6355251</p>	

Introduction

In this globalization era, companies will develop through of doing their business activities creatively and innovatively to show their superiority to expand the market for the products they produce. The market is filled with various products that compete fiercely. To win the competition, each company will look for workers who are competent in their fields and have high employability. Therefore, companies pay attention to human resource development to improve job performance. Various methods have been used by the company to increase maximum job performance in realizing the company's vision and mission. Every worker is required to have high job performance. Job performance is the result of employee performance to achieve the targets set by the company. High job performance is the main target in the companies success in achieving its goals.

Performance in organization is a measured of a companies capacity in achieving individual goals which can be assessed through job performance. Job performance is a very important issue not only for companies but also the researchers in a field the management in a organisational psychology. Job performance appraisal is very important to provide feedback for employees in improving performance, reward adjustment, job placement, training and development, career development, evaluation of companies, to feedback for the human resources department to measure their success in carrying out departmental functions in organisation.

Job performance is a work achieved by each employee for their job. Every employee has a different job performance which is shown by it knowledge and skills. Employees who show their attitudes can be seen from dedication, discipline, knowledge, skills, and responsibility for their work. The attitude of employees towards work reflects their commitment to work. The commitment of employees to work is a reflection of their responsibilities towards the job. Job performance records many factors that influence it, both individual and group, such as work environment, job satisfaction, job loyalty, organisational culture, and organisational commitment (Saeed et al., 2013; Putriana et all, 2015; Muis et all, 2018). Broadly speaking, the determinants of job performance can be grouped into individual and group factors. Individual factors include work motivation, work commitment, job satisfaction, and stress levels. Meanwhile, organisational factors include the physical conditions of work, compensation, and job design.

Lawler (1991) defines that job performance is a job achievement by employees in their duties and jobs efficiently and effectively. Bangun (2012) reveal that job performance is a measure of individual performance that can be assessed qualitatively and quantitatively. Based on its quality, performance can be measured to what extent the process or implementation of activities approaches perfection in accordance with the expected goals, while quantitatively it is related to the quantity produced, for example it can be measured through money, unit value, and finalization of activities (Bernadi & Russel, 1993). Job performance can be seen from the results of

employee work through work discipline, responsibility, work ability as measured by knowledge and skills, and loyalty to work. Based on preliminary information, it shows that the employees' knowledge, skills and work discipline are good, but the job performance of Bank X has decreased. This phenomenon indicates that there is a gap between expectations and reality experienced by Bank X.

Research results indicate that corporate culture is one of the factors to impact of job performance. Corporate culture is one of the important factors in increasing the competitiveness of a company, so it is a key factor to determine the success of company in achieving its goals (Bangun, 2008; Kotter and Heskett, 2006). The success of the company in achieving its objectives depends on the strength or weakness of the organisational culture in its application. Weak business management will result in low individual productivity (Bangun, 2014). The employees who have good competence can to jointly the increase of strongg the corporate culture to achieve goals (Bangun, 2008). Organizational culture is defined as a system that has beliefs, values, and the norms in an organisation (Gibson et al., 1997). Whereas Schein (1992) defines that Organisational Culture as a model the basic assumptions including a creating, discovereing, and developing by certain groups when they adapt to internal and external problems that well job have value and learn of new members in organisation about the right way to solve organisational problems.

Another factor that affects of job performance is an Organisational Commitment (Bangun, 2006). In the work, employee commitment to the organisation is an important issue in which every party, both workers and employers, is very important to understand the meaning of commitment to create conducive working conditions (Bangun, 2006). In general that the Organisational Commitment the defined as a provision that is mutually agreed upon by every individual in the organisation as a guideline, implementation, and goals to be achieved in the future (Muis et al. 2018). Meyer et al (1998) reveal that there are three main components in organisational commitment was included the normative, affective, and continuance commitment. The normative commitment occurs when employees become the members of organisation causally of awareness the commitment in organisation is should be done. Affective commitment occured that the employees wish into the part of an organisation causally of the emotional bond. Meanwhile, continuance commitment occured that the employees wish in an organization because they need a salary or profit, or other reasons such as not finding another job. The reseach aims to the analyze to effect the organisational commitment and organizational culture toward the job performance.

Job performance is a determine factor for the survival of the company, especially for companies engaged in services such as banking companies. The job performed by each employee is an activity that is carried out continuously. Every employee is faced with routine work that is done every day which can cause boredom. This condition, if not corrected immediately, can reduce the level of employee commitment to their work. Other factors can cause a weak organisational culture. The continuous decline in job performance creates serious problems and has an impact on the decline in company profits.

Previous studies have stated that the organisational culture there to effect on the job performance. Metin & Asli (2018) stated that organisational commitment in the workplace has a potential influence on organisational effectiveness and job performance. This can be explained that employees who are committed will have integrity in completing their duties and goals. Commitment can be expressed continuously to doing the tasks in goals achieving, service quality, accepting changes, and extra tasks. Theoretically, organisational commitment can be related to job performance..

Organizational Commitment on Job Performance

Allen and Mayer (1997) suggest that both normative and affective commitments are related to employee achievement or performance, whereas continuance commitment is often unrelated or even negatively related. This shows that employees who have a commitment to the organisation will show more effort in their workplace. This fact show that there are accordance with the research result that providing empirical evidence that organisational commitment to effect on job performance a directly and significantly. The research results show that there are effect of organisational commitment on job performance are suggested which conditioning that organisational commitment to effect on the job performance a significantly and positively. This research results are also supported that the organisational commitment and job performance is relationships a positively.

Organizational commitment describes how far a person identifies and involves himself in his organization and the desire to remain in that organization (Greenberg and Baron, 1997). Organizational commitment can be seen as the relative strength of the individual in identifying his involvement in the organization (Porter, Mowday and Steers, 1992). On the other hand, Robbins (2001) views that organizational commitment is one of the work attitudes that can reflect one's feelings which include loyalty, identification and involvement. Basically, organizational commitment is a process that each individual can identify with the values, rules, and goals of the organization.

The fact show that organizational commitment is not just passive loyalty to the organization but is actively involved in achieving goals. Employees who have a high commitment involve themselves to work well and are responsible for supporting the welfare and success of the organization. Employees will feel bound to the

organization so as to create job satisfaction which has an impact on work performance. Employees who have high organizational commitment show that these employees carry out obligations, responsibilities, and promises that limit a person's freedom to do something. In other words, employees who have a high commitment to their work will prioritize the interests of the organization's. On the other hand, organizational commitment means the existence of a person's superiority in acting in line with his promises to the organization. The higher the degree of employee commitment to the organization, the higher the work performance achieved. However, in practice not all employees carry out organizational commitments as a whole. Some employees have very high commitment and some are low.

The factors that influence the degree of commitment of a person are intrinsic and extrinsic factors of the employee concerned. Employee intrinsic factors may include aspects of the employee's family socio-economic conditions, age, education, work experience, personality stability, and gender. On the other hand, extrinsic factors include exemplary management, especially top management, in being committed to various aspects of the organization. Extrinsic factors outside the organization include aspects of culture, macroeconomic conditions, job opportunities, and competition for compensation.

Organisational Culture and Job Performance

The previous research have showed that organisational culture to effect on job performance a significant. The research result shows that the strong organisational culture will have a positive effect on job performance (Tjahjadi, 2001). This is supported by a strong organisational culture which causes employees to have a clear orientation to complete their job responsibilities. In other words, employees will be able to improve their job performance, and vice versa.

Each company has a distinctive organizational culture that describes the characteristics of each company in relation to work performance. Organizational culture describes a value system which is a collective agreement of all involved in the company. A value system is a conception of value that lives in the realm of thought of a group of individuals and management. Organizational culture is closely related to the perception of values and the environment. Perception will give birth to meaning and outlook on life that will affect the attitudes and behavior of employees and management at work. Organizational culture can be actualized very diversely in achieving organizational goals. Organizational culture can be manifested in the form of loyalty, responsibility, cooperation, discipline, honesty, perseverance, enthusiasm, quality of work, fairness, and personality integrity. All forms of actualization of organizational culture are related to organizational commitment. Every act, dedication, and loyalty of a person to the promise he has made to fulfill his organizational and individual goals.

A study by Kang and Steward (2007) shows there are a positively effect between organisational culture and job performance. Similar results are shown by a study by Cameron and Quinn (2011) so that they recommend that decision makers in organisations can provide aspirations for employees to develop a strong organisational culture. Almatari and Omira (2017) conducted a study in Saudi Arabia involving 389 respondents in the public sector. The research results indicate that strong relationship between organisational culture and job performance. Job performance is an employee's will as an acknowledgment of his loyalty to work. High job performance becomes an expectation for every worker as a basis for receiving awards. Companies often use job performance as the basis for promotion and determination of the amount of compensation. For workers, job performance is used as the basis for a job career. On the company side, job performance is part of the company's performance as measured by the level of profit the company receives. Every employee wants to achieve job performance, but this will requires adequate abilities, skills and knowledge. Therefore, a growing company will develop its employees to improve their job performance.

Thus, job performance is the result of work shown by each employee for their work. Job performance is basically individual in nature, so the ability level of an employee and every opportunity an employee gets is different. However, in reality, job performance can occur in work groups. Therefore, this is the reason for the difficulty of measuring individual job performance in the work group. Job performance appraisal is important both for the employees themselves and for the company in determining the ranking of companies in the industry. Performance appraisal is an activity to evaluate the job performance that has been achieved by employees.

Several previous research results indicate that there is an influence of Organisational Commitment and Organisational Culture. Bangun (2006; 2008) shows that a strong organisational culture and organisational commitment will affect company productivity and competitiveness. A study in Danar Hadi shows that a professional family culture in the family company is a driving force for organisational excellence (Moeljono, 2005). The results of research conducted by Kotter and Heskett show that corporate culture can have an impact on individuals. Harrison and Hubard (1998) say that organisational commitment is related to individual performance and organizational success. The description of several the results of studies, the model and hypothesis the following was in this study:

Figure 1. Research Model.

Method

Population, Sample, and Sampling Technique

This research was conducted for all permanent employees at Bank X in the city of Bandung with a total of 100 people. Sampling using the following Slovin formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} \tag{1}$$

where N is a population, n is a sample, and e is the error rate of 5 percent. Based on this formula, the sample size employee is 78. Sampling of technique was used was the simple random sampling.

Collecting Data Method

The techniques of data collection used are secondary and primary data. Secondary data is a literature study obtained from Bank X regarding employee data relating to the number of employees, knowledge, and skills. Primary data was conducted by observing the employees behavior of Bank X, interviews were conducted directly on several employees of Bank X, and distributed questionnaires to employees against a number of samples that had been determined.

Data Analysis Technique

The data analysis technique uses path analysis to knowing the effect of Organisational Commitment and the Organisational Culture on the Job Performance, either partially or simultaneously. Path analysis produces path coefficients by calculating the correlation among of independent variables and the dependent variable. This research there are three pathways consisting of two regression lines and one correlation path by calculating the magnitude of the effect of Organisational Commitment (X₁) on Job Performance (Y), Organisational Culture (X₂) on Job Performance (Y), and the correlation between Organizational Commitment. (X₁) with Organizational Culture (X₂) on Work Performance (Y). Based on the research hypothesis, there are three equations to test the hypothesis, as follows:

$$Y = \rho_{yx_1}X_1 + \epsilon_1 \tag{2}$$

$$Y = \rho_{yx_2}X_2 + \epsilon_2 \tag{3}$$

$$Y = \rho_{yx_1}X_1 + \rho_{yx_2}X_2 + \epsilon_3 \tag{4}$$

To test the hypothesis using the following formula:

$$\text{Hypothesis 1: } H_0 : \rho_{yx_1} = 0 ; H_a : \rho_{yx_1} > 0 \tag{5}$$

$$\text{Hypothesis 2: } H_0 : \rho_{yx_2} = 0 ; H_a : \rho_{yx_2} > 0 \tag{6}$$

$$\rho_{yx_2}X_2 = 0 ; H_0 : \rho_{yx_1} = \rho_{yx_2} \neq 0 \tag{7}$$

Validity and Reliability Testing

A measurement instrument is said to be good if it meets the validity and reliability criteria. The validity testing was carrying out to determine the extent of the differences obtained through the measurement tools used, reflecting the actual differences with the respondents studied. The reliability testing is carried out to estimate of extent to which the measurement instrument used is free from random or unstable errors, meaning that this reliability test is intended

In this study, testing the validity of using Product Moment correlation by correlating the scores on the items with the total item scores (Ashari & Santosa, 2005). The instrument is said to be valid if it measures what should be measured, and meets the requirements, namely items are positively correlated with a factor and a maximum p-value of 0.05 in the one tail test. Reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha with the Rule of thumb must be more than 0.6 is still accepted (Hair et., al., 1998; Sekaran, 2010).

Results and Discussion

The research results shows that organisational culture effect on job performance of 0.865 or 86.5 percent a level of significant by 0.00, this indicates that two variables have a strong relationship a significantly. Organisational Commitment has a effect on Job Performance by 0.484 or 48.4 percent at level of significance is 0.00, this indicates shows that the relationships between two variables is sufficient and significant. Then Organisational Commitment with Organisational Culture has a relationship of 0.488 or 48.8 percent and a significantly at level of 0.00. This shows that there are the relationship between the two variables is sufficient and significant.

Testing hypothesis using path analysis to knowing the effect of the Organisational Culture and the Organisational Commitment on Job Performance. The statistics output shows that the hypothesis testing in the Table 1.

Table 1. Coefecient

Models	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Significant
	B	Standard Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.499	4.694		-.106	.916
1 Organisational Commitment	.069	.056	.080	1.240	.219
Organisational Culture	.630	.049	.826	12.732	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance

The statistics output in Table 1 shows that an equation the simple linear regression is $Y = -0,499 + 0.069 X_1 + 0.630 X_2$. This equation shows that the constant value is -0.499, if job performance is not influenced by organisational culture and organisational commitment, then the average employee job performance is -0.499. Organisational culture coefficient with a value of 0.630 indicates that organisational culture has the effect on Job Performance. Each occurs the increase in the variable of organisational culture by one percent will increasing the job performance by 0.630 percent. Likewise, any increase in the Organisational Commitment variable will increase Job Performance by 0.069 percent.

Table 1 shows that equations (2), (3), and (4) of the statistic output are as follows:

$$Y = 0,080X_1 + 0,174E_1 \quad (8)$$

$$Y = 0,826X_2 + 0,020E_2 \quad (9)$$

$$Y = 0,080X_1 + 0,826X_2 + 0,247E_3 \quad (10)$$

Table 2 shows that Organisational Culture and Organisational Commitment variables are predictor variables of the Job Performance. This can be seen based on the F count of 117.58 at the level of significance of 0.000. Based on a sig. value ≤ 0.05 , this indicates show that the regression models can using to predict of job performance variable.

Table 2. ANOVA^a

Models	Sum of Square	d.f.	Mean Square	F	Significant
1 Regression	6546.794	2	3273.397	117.578	.000 ^b
Residual	2143.694	77	27.840		
Total	8690.488	79			

- a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Commitment Organisation, Culture Organisation.

Following section, hypothesis testing will be presented partially on hypotheses one and two a simultaneously. The first hypothesis, based on statistical results, shows that Organisational Culture has a sig value. = 0.000 < 0.05. This means that Organisational Commitment and Organisational Culture partially effect on Job Performance. In the table 2, it is found that the t count for the Organisational Culture variable is 12.732, which is greater than the ttable of 1.980, this indicates show that Organisational Culture effect on Job Performance a significantly. Organisational culture is strong in a company will increase the employee's job performance.

Results of this research indicates how important it's to create the strong organisational culture in an organisation. Organisational culture is strong when there is a common vision, values and beliefs to achieving the goals that the organisation has set. Organisational culture describes identity, unifies organisations, reduces conflict, commitment to groups, reduces uncertainty, creates consistency, motivation, performance, work safety, and sources of competitive advantage. Schein (2004) defining that organisational culture as a model the basic assumption that can be learning by an organization in solving the problems it faces from external adjustment and internal integrations, has working well and is considering valuable, therefore it is training of the new workers, thinking, and feeling in a relationship to the problem. Every organization has a different culture to achieve its goals. In a company, corporate culture is a key aspect of an organization (Bangun, 2008).

Employees who have understood the overall values of the organization will make these values a part of themselves and their lives. A value and belief for each employee will be manifested in their behavior at work. The results of research by Chatman and Bersade (1997) and Udan Bintoro (2002) state that a strong organizational culture can improve organizational performance. Organizational culture is a factor that has a major contribution in improving work performance because it is related to organizational effectiveness to support the achievement of organizational goals (Bangun, 2008). A strong organizational culture will prove the achievement of increasing job performance. If the organizational culture has been agreed as a corporate strategy, the organizational culture can be used as a tool to improve the job performance. Organizational culture has a significant effect on effectiveness in the achieving organizational goals and work performance. Organizational culture is very influential on the effectiveness of the work carried out and adjusted to the characteristics of the work which ultimately has an impact on work performance. Organizational culture has a function as a mechanism that creates meaning and can shape the attitudes and behavior of employees and leaders in the organization. Indirectly will be able to create a mechanism that streamlines the work of the organization concerned.

Figure 2: Result of Research.

Conclusion

Based on the conclusions of this study, there are several suggestions, including on each variable. For the Organisational Commitment variable: as an indicator of this variable, there are still some employees who work in other jobs outside Bank X. This side job will make employees not focus on doing it optimally. A small proportion of employees do not understand their work well, this happens because these employees do not want to develop themselves. For the Organisational Culture variable, a small proportion of employees are less obedient to company rules and regulations. Therefore, the company should provide training and development for employees on a regular basis in order to increase their responsibility and loyalty to work and the company.

The company must clearly socialize the rules and regulations of the company to employees so that the organisational culture is stronger.

Recommendations

The results of the study indicate that there are still some employees who work on other jobs outside Bank of X. This side job will make employees not focus on doing it optimally. A small number of employees do not understand their work well, this happens because the employee does not want to develop himself. A small number of employees do not obey the company's rules and regulations. Therefore, the company should provide training and development for employees on a regular basis to be able to increase their responsibility and loyalty to the work and the company. The company must clearly socialize the rules and regulations of the company to employees so that the organizational culture is stronger.
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